

Reaction for each variety was determined by the ratio of final population to initial population. Five varieties showed resistance to

Hirschmanniella spp. in the field: Kao Paung Klang, Kao Paung, Kao Tah Jue, Kao Yaun, and Kao Klang Pee (see table). *ℓ*

Field reaction of rice varieties to *Hirschmanniella* spp. Patumthani Rice Research Center, Thailand.

Variety	Nematodes ^a (no./300 cc soil)	Pf/Pi ^b	Reaction ^c
Kao Paung Klang	224 a	1.54	R
Kao Paung	237 a	1.63	R
Kao Tah Jue	254 a	1.75	R
Kao Yaun	258 ab	1.78	R
Kao Klang Pee	288 ab	1.98	R
RD9	319 a	2.20	I
Tah Lee	322 ab	2.22	I
Mali Thong	351 abc	2.42	I
Kao Tah Ex	390 abc	2.69	I
Tah Chue	438 abc	3.02	I
IR45	530 abc	3.65	I
Kao Nam Kem	579 abc	3.99	I
TN1	707 bc	4.87	I
Kao Kun Na	785 abc	5.41	S
Kao Pla Lai	896 bc	6.17	S
IR26	1012 c	6.97	S
Kao Ko Dew	1524 c	10.50	S

^aAv of 4 replications. ^bPf = final population at 60 d after transplanting, Pi = initial population. ^cBased on Pf/Pi: R = < 2.0, I = 2.1 - 5.0, and S = > 5.0.

discolored seed and induced longitudinal necrosis in sheath and leaves. When inoculated on plants in the boot stage by leaf-clip or stem injection, the same isolates induced sheath blotching and severe grain discoloration without longitudinal necrosis.

Some varieties apparently recovered following inoculation, with leaf symptoms diminishing on new leaves as they emerged. However, even when the boot was symptomless, the panicle emerged with discolored grain, from which the pathogen could be reisolated. Similar cases have been observed in farmers' fields.

Seed from plants showing glume discoloration, washed and incubated on King's B medium, yielded the pathogen. Up to 100% of the seed from affected plants yielded fluorescent bacteria. When discolored seed was planted without prior breaking of dormancy with dry heat, seedlings showed symptoms within 30 d of emergence.

The pathogen also was consistently recovered from symptomless leaves prior to symptom expression. Severely affected seedlings died, but most survived to flowering. Seed

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Bacterial sheath brown rot (BSBR) in Latin America

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In rice, disease symptoms identical to those of BSBR, caused by *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae*, have been observed in Guatemala, Panama, Colombia, Surinam, Peru, and Brazil for 10 years. Symptoms include 2-5 mm wide longitudinal brown necrosis of the sheath, sometimes extending its full length. In some cases the lesions extend to the leaf margin or midrib, producing a pronounced stripe (see figure). All leaves of a tiller may be affected.

On some varieties, symptoms are more diffuse, resulting in a brown to maroon blotching with no apparent leaf blade symptoms. The sheath margin

often withers. When the flag leaf sheath is affected, water-soaking may occur.

Preemergence and postemergence panicles from affected flag leaf sheaths invariably show substantial glume discoloration with severely discolored often unfilled grains. Panicles may not emerge completely from affected sheaths.

A rod-shaped, multiflagellate (polar) bacterium producing fluorescent pigments on King's B medium was consistently isolated from plants exhibiting these symptoms. Inoculating healthy plants grown from healthy, heat-treated seed with the isolates reproduced the symptoms. Subsequent characterization and pathogenicity tests showed the pathogen to be indistinguishable from *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae*.

When inoculated on 15- and 40-d-old plants, isolates formed longitudinal necrotic lesions, blotched sheaths, and

a) Necrotic stripe symptoms caused by *P. fuscovaginae*. b) Discoloration and necrosis of sheath caused by *P. fuscovaginae*, CIAT, Cali, Colombia. Necrosis extends to the margin of the flag leaf. Note similarity to sheath rot caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (*Acrocyndrium*).

transmission exceeded 75% in some experiments.

Results of experiments to evaluate heat therapy's ability to eradicate the pathogen from infected seed are presented in the table. Moderate dry heat therapy substantially reduced pathogen recovery from seed, but 65°C for 6 d was required to completely eradicate it. No deleterious effect on germination was detected by even higher heat treatment (70°C, 6 d).

Although this is the first report of sheath rot and grain discoloration caused by *Pseudomonas* spp. in Latin America, BSBR has probably been in the region for some time. BSBR has been reported in Japan and in high-altitude rice in Burundi, East Africa. A disease with identical symptomatology, but attributed to an unidentified bacterium, has been reported in southern Brazil (bacterial brown stripe). Reports of dirty panicle, glume discoloration, and manchado de grano have been increasing around the world.

The striking similarity between the sheath symptoms described and those attributed to *Sarocladium oryzae* (sheath rot), combined with the

Effect of heat treatment on recovery of *P. fuscovaginae* from spotted seed of 2 varieties,^a CIAT, Cali, Colombia.

Temperature (°C)	Recovery of <i>P. fuscovaginae</i>					
	1 d		3 d		6 d	
	Infected seed (no.)	Total seed (no.)	Infected seed (no.)	Total seed (no.)	Infected seed (no.)	Total seed (no.)
	<i>CICA8</i>					
55	107	396	235	418	24	333
60	153	591	56	443	9	350
65	22	584	2	227	0	401
Control (untreated seed)	233	339	235	396	280	431
	<i>Oryzica 1</i>					
55	102	421	105	338	12	374
60	47	377	38	369	5	234
65	18	375	12	375	0	403
Control (untreated seed)	318	400	115	327	115	383

^aInfection identified by pathogenic fluorescent bacteria on King's B medium.

difficulty researchers often encounter reisolating *S. oryzae* from the grain, suggest that symptoms attributed to the fungus in some cases may be caused by *P. fuscovaginae*. In Colombia, symptomatology and the association of this bacterium with dirty panicle suggest that it is among the primary causal agents.

CIAT has detected the pathogen in seed received in routine international germplasm exchanges from Asia and Africa. At CIAT, all seed received from and seed sent to national and international programs is treated with dry heat at 65°C and monitored to ensure that it is free of the bacterium. *J*

In vitro response of maize and rice isolates of *Rhizoctonia solani* to antibiotics and fungitoxicants

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We tested the effect of two antibiotics and five fungitoxicants on *Rhizoctonia solani* f. sp. *sasakii* using the food-poison technique and maize (R₁) and rice (R₆) isolates. Radial growth was measured at 24-h intervals.

Carbendazim, benodanil, and thiabendazole at 25-30 µg ai/ml completely inhibited growth of both isolates and showed fungistatic effects (see table). Both isolates were less sensitive to thiophanate-M, dichloroline, and aureofungin. Isolate

Fungitoxicant and antibiotic effect on radial growth of 2 *R. solani* isolates in vitro.^a

Fungitoxicant, antibiotic	Concentration (µg/ml)	Growth reduction (%)	
		Maize isolate	Rice isolate
Validamycin A	30.0	24.0	22.0
	36.0	24.5	24.5
	45.0	27.0	22.0
Aureofungin	3.0	39.5	56.0
	6.0	41.0	45.3
Benodanil	25.0	100.0	100.0
	37.5	100.0	100.0
	50.0	100.0	100.0
Carbendazim	25.0	100.0	100.0
	31.5	100.0	100.0
	50.0	100.0	100.0
Dichloroline	30.0	30.0	42.0
	60.0	30.0	39.0
	120.0	33.0	39.0
Thiabendazole	30.0	100.0	100.0
	45.0	100.0	100.0
	60.0	100.0	100.0
Thiophanate-methyl	35.0	100.0	45.0
	56.5	100.0	32.0
	70.0	100.0	30.0

^aAv of 3 replications.